

Twenty three species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) new to the fauna of Poland

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ABSTRACT. Twenty three species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) new to the fauna of Poland.

New distributional records of twenty three species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) are given, all reported for the first time from Poland: *Gastrotrypes caudatus* BRUES, *Leptacis coryphe* BUHL, *Platygaster betularia* KIEFFER, *P. damokles* (BUHL), *P. frater* BUHL, *P. germanica* BUHL, *P. gracilipes* HUGGERT, *P. microsculpturata* BUHL, *P. philinna* WALKER, *P. robiniae* BUHL & DUSO, *P. signata* (FOERSTER), *P. soederlundi* BUHL, *P. splendidula* RUTHE, *P. striatithorax* BUHL, *P. varicornis* BUHL, *Prosactogaster erdosi* SZELENYI, *Synopeas convexum* THOMSON, *S. doczkali* BUHL, *S. fungorum* BUHL, *S. jasius* (WALKER), *S. noyesi* BUHL, *S. osaces* (WALKER) and *Trichacis pisis* (WALKER). The new records increase the number of Platygastriinae known to occur in Poland to 124 species.

KEY WORDS: Hymenoptera, Platygastroidea, Platygastriidae, Platygastriinae; faunistics, new records, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

Since the synopsis of GARBARCZYK (1997), who listed from Poland 56 species of Platygastriinae (i.e., Platygastriidae excluding Scelionidae and Sceliotrachelidae, as accepted by most authors today), a substantial progress has been made in the faunistic study of this group of tiny parasitoid wasps. Two species, *Synopeas bialowiezaensis* BUHL, 2005 and *Platygaster polonica* BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI, 2016a were described based on specimens known only from Poland, and *Inostemma kaponeni* BUHL, 2005 was described from Finland and Poland. Sixteen species were recorded for the first time from Poland by BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2016b), the male of *Synopeas burgeri* BUHL, 2012, a species known so far only from the German female holotype, was discovered in Poland and described (BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2016a), and most recently BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2017) discovered another 25 species previously not known to occur in Poland. As a result, the checklist of the Platygastriinae of Poland nearly doubled from 2005 to 2017. As mentioned in previous studies (BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2016b, 2017), the Platygastriinae fauna of Poland still remains poorly known, as the 101 recorded species is a small number compared to 260 spp. known from the British Isles (BUHL & NOTTON 2009) or ca. 220 spp. found in Denmark and Fennoscandia (BUHL 1999).

The present study is a continuation of the recently initiated faunistic survey of the Platygastriinae of Poland, and below we give records of 23 species previously not known from this country.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens were collected using a sweeping net, by the second author, unless stated otherwise; the exception is *Synopeas doczkali*, reared from stem galls on *Salix*. All voucher specimens are dry-mounted on points and deposited in the collection of the second author, Wrocław, Poland. The previously known distributional data are given after the Hymenoptera Online (<http://hol.osu.edu>) and a personal database of the first author. Data on known hosts, if available, are given after the same sources. We acknowledge Rafał Ruta and Marek Wanat (University of Wrocław) for providing interesting material from their collections.

RESULTS

Gastrotrypes caudatus BRUES, 1922 (Fig. 1)

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 23.04.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: cosmopolitan; host unknown.

Leptacis coryphe BUHL, 1998 (Fig. 2)

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 11.06.2016, 1♂.

Distribution: Scandinavia and Finland, British Isles; host unknown.

Platygaster betularia KIEFFER, 1916

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 03.04.2017, 1♀; 10.07.2017, 2♀♀.

Distribution: Very common in West Europe, also recorded from Mongolia. Host: *Semudobia betulae* (WINNERTZ) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on *Betula* spp.

Platygaster damokles (BUHL, 1998)

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [WT18] Gryżyna vic., meadow “Augustynka”, 04.06.2016, 1♀, leg. R. Ruta.

Distribution: NW Europe, rare; host unknown.

Platygaster frater BUHL, 2006 (Fig. 3)

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 30.04.2016, 1♀, 30.04.2016, 1♀.

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, meadow and deciduous forest edge along Widawa Riv., 12.05.2017, 4♀♀, 1♂.

Distribution: Common in West Europe; host unknown.

Platygaster germanica BUHL, 1998

Roztocze: [FB51] Kąty II ad Zamość, Wieprzecka Góra, 28.06.2016, 1♀, leg. M. Wanat.

Distribution: West Europe, rare; host unknown.

Platygaster gracilipes HUGGERT, 1975**Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland:** [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 22.05.2017, 1♀.Distribution: Holarctic, common. Host: *Sitodiplosis mosellana* (GÉHIN) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on wheat.***Platygaster microsculpturata*** BUHL, 1999**Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland:** [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 04.08.2017, 4♀♀.Distribution: NW Europe, reaching Latvia in the east, rather rare. Host: *Dasineura violae* (F. LOEW) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on *Viola odorata* L.***Platygaster philinna*** WALKER, 1835**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, railway embankment, 18.05.2017, 1♀; [XS34] Rolantowice ad Wrocław, sandpit, 15.06.2017, 1♀, leg. M. Wanat.

Distribution: NW Europe, moderately common; host unknown.

Platygaster robiniae BUHL & DUSO, 2008**Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland:** [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 04.08.2017, 5♀♀.**Lower Silesia:** [XS46] Wrocław, city center, lawn at the Herbarium building of the Natural History Museum, 16.07.2017, 1♀.Host: the locust gall midge *Obolodiplosis robiniae* HALDEMAN (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), developing on leaves of *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. Both the tree and its pest are alien (North American) species in European fauna; the locust gall midge was recorded from Europe (Italy) for the first time in 2003, and from Poland in 2008 (DUSO & SKUHRAVA 2004, SKRZYPCZYŃSKA 2008). The parasitoid of *O. robiniae*, *P. robiniae*, was described based on specimens reared in Italy; it is also known to occur in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Croatia, France, Switzerland, Scandinavia, China and Japan; certainly its distribution is much broader.***Platygaster signata*** (FOERSTER, 1861)**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 21.07.2016, 3♂♂, 2♀♀.

Distribution: Europe to Mongolia, rare; host unknown.

Platygaster soederlundi BUHL, 1998**Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland:** [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, mixed dark forest, 10.07.2017, 1♀.**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 10.07.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: Europe to Mongolia, rather rare; host unknown.

Platygaster splendidula RUTHE, 1859**Lower Silesia:** [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, meadow near deciduous forest edge, Umbelliferae and cane, 11.06.2017, 1♀.Distribution: West Europe to Mongolia (possibly also Korea), common. Host: *Mayetiola schoberi* BARNES (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on *Poa pratensis* (L.).

Platygaster striatithorax BUHL, 1994

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, railway embankment, 12.05.2017, 1♂.

Distribution: NW Europe, moderately common; host unknown.

Platygaster varicornis BUHL, 1999

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, deciduous forest and meadows along Widawa Riv., 11.06.2017, 1♀.

Distribution: Sweden and Denmark, very rare; host unknown.

Prosactogaster erdosi SZELENYI, 1958 (Fig. 4)

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [WT18] Gryżyna vic., meadow 'Augustynka', 04.06.2016, 2♀♀, leg. R. Ruta.

Distribution: Hungary, Romania, rare. Host: an unspecified cecidomyiid on *Phragmites australis* (CAV.) STEUD.

Synopeas convexum THOMSON, 1859

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, sandy bank of Wisła Riv., 17.09.2015, 1♀; [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, sandy hill at a pine forest edge, 10.07.2017, 1♀.

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, deciduous forest and meadows along Widawa Riv., 11.06.2016, 2♀♀.

Distribution: NW Europe, moderately common; host unknown.

Synopeas doczkali BUHL, 2010 (Fig. 5)

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, reared from stem galls on *Salix* sp., galls leg. 30.04.2016, adults emerged 05.2017, 2♂♂.

This species has been known only from females; males (Fig. 5) are here reported for the first time. Known to occur in Germany and Sweden, very rare; host unknown.

Synopeas fungorum BUHL, 2000

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, 30.04.2016, 2♀♀, 10.07.2017, 1♀.

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 23.06.2016, 1♀.

Distribution: West Europe to Finland and Latvia, rare. Host: unknown Cecidomyiidae on fungi *Meripilus giganteus* (PERS.) and *Laetiporus sulphureus* (BULL. ex FRIES).

Synopeas jasius (WALKER, 1835)

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, deciduous forest along Widawa Riv., 12.05.2017, 1♂.

Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia, Hungary, moderately rare. Host: unknown Cecidomyiidae in freshly cut ends of logs of *Quercus* sp., *Fraxinus* sp. and *Acer* sp.

***Synopeas noyesi* BUHL, 2009**

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 03.07.2016, 1♀; .

Distribution: British Isles, Germany, Scandinavia, moderately rare; host unknown.

***Synopeas osaces* (WALKER, 1835)**

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [XU58] nature reserve Zielona Góra ad Osiek, 12.2014, 1♀, leg. R. Ruta.

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, deciduous forest along Widawa Riv., 12.05.2017, 1♀; [XS46] Wrocław, city center, lawn at the Herbarium building of the Natural History Museum, 16.07.2017, 2♀♀.

Distribution: West Europe, Mongolia, Korea, United Arab Emirates. Host: *Contarinia medicaginis* KIEFFER (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) on *Medicago* sp.

***Trichacis pisis* (WALKER, 1835) (Fig. 6)**

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, 23.04.2016, 2♂♂; 18.05.2017, 1♂.

Distribution: British Isles, Scandinavia, Finland, Germany, Spain, rather common; host unknown.

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of the Platygastriinae fauna of Poland grows rapidly; since the end of the XXth c. 68 species previously not known from the Polish territory have been recorded. GARBARCZYK (1997) listed only 56 spp.; recent intensification of collecting efforts focused on this subfamily resulted in increasing this number to 124. It should be noted that the majority of the recently recorded species come from a few localities only, mainly around the cities of Wrocław and Poznań in the western part of the country, and from SE Poland (BUHL & JALOSZYŃSKI 2016a, b, 2017). An estimation of over 250 species to occur in Poland seems justified, based on much better studied British Isles or Denmark and Fennoscandia, where the diversity of potential hosts and plant associates of Platygastriinae is certainly not greater than that in Poland.

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STRESZCZENIE

Dwadzieścia trzy gatunki Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) nowe dla fauny Polski

Od końca XX wieku liczba gatunków Platygastriinae znanych z terytorium Polski wzrosła z 56 do 124. Dwadzieścia trzy z tych gatunków podane zostały jako nowe dla Polski w niniejszej pracy: *Gastrotrypes caudatus* BRUES, *Leptacis coryphe* BUHL, *Platygaster betularia* KIEFFER, *P. damokles* (BUHL), *P. frater* BUHL, *P. germanica* BUHL, *P. gracilipes* HUGGERT, *P. microsculpturata* BUHL, *P. philinna* WALKER, *P. robiniae* BUHL & DUSO, *P. signata* (FOERSTER), *P. soederlundi* BUHL, *P. splendidula* RUTHE, *P. striatithorax* BUHL, *P. varicornis* BUHL, *Prosactogaster erdosi* SZELENYI, *Synopeas convexum* THOMSON, *S. doczkali* BUHL, *S. fungorum* BUHL, *S. jasius* (WALKER), *S. noyesi* BUHL, *S. osaces* (WALKER) and *Trichacis pisis* (WALKER). Wszystkie dawniejsze rekordy wymagają weryfikacji, głównie ze względu na bardzo dużą trudność oznaczania Platygastriinae i już potwierdzoną możliwość występowania w naszym kraju gatunków nowych dla nauki. Biorąc pod uwagę występowanie w naszym kraju warunków środowiskowych zbliżonych do tych na obszarach dużo lepiej zbadanych (np. Wyspy Brytyjskie, Dania i Fennoskandia), rzeczywistą liczbę polskich Platygastriinae można szacować na przekraczającą 250 spp. Większa część terytorium Polski pozostaje praktycznie niezbadana pod kątem występowania Platygastriinae, a większość spośród ok. 60 gatunków wykazanych po raz pierwszy w ciągu ostatnich kilku lat pochodzi ze zbiorów na Dolnym Śląsku, Nizinie Wielkopolsko-Kujawskiej oraz z południowo-wschodniego krańca kraju.

Figs 1–6. Examples of newly recorded Platygasterinae: *Gastrotrypes caudatus* (1), *Leptacis coryphae* (2), *Platygaster frater* (3), *Prosactogaster erdosi* (4), *Synopeas doczkali* (5), and *Trichacis pisis* (6) (photos P. Jąłoszyński).

Ryc. 1–6. Przykłady nowo stwierdzonych Platygasterinae: *Gastrotrypes caudatus* (1), *Leptacis coryphae* (2), *Platygaster frater* (3), *Prosactogaster erdosi* (4), *Synopeas doczkali* (5) i *Trichacis pisis* (6) (fot. P. Jąłoszyński).

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